

EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF REINFORCING EFFECTS OF FRP SHEETS BONDED ON MORTAR AND CONCRETE BEAMS

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SUMMARY: Much attention has recently been paid in recent years to rehabilitation such as repair and preservation of infrastructure using fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) sheets. This study is aimed at establishing some theoretical basis and guidelines for such applications by examining the failure process and the increased fracture toughness of mortar and concrete beams reinforced with carbon and glass fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP, GFRP) sheets. Two kinds of beam specimens with and without a center notch were prepared and subjected to three-point flexure: large specimen of concrete reinforced with GFRP or CFRP sheets and small specimen of mortar reinforced with GFRP sheets. The failure process as well as load, strain and crack opening displacement behavior were monitored by acoustic emission (AE) activity. The relation between reinforcing effect and fracture toughness at the initiation of AE activity is discussed based on these results.

KEYWORDS: rehabilitation of infrastructure, GFRP sheets, CFRP sheets, reinforcing effects, mortar and concrete beams, failure process, fracture toughness, acoustic emission

INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure might be damaged by earthquake, fatigue, overload or severe and long term environmental attacks during service. So rehabilitation of infrastructure is an obviously necessity. Bonding thin steel plates to critical areas of concrete subjected to tensile loading has been shown to be an effective strengthening method [1]. Over the past decade, high strength, light weight fiber reinforced plastics (FRP), primarily developed for aerospace and other industrial applications, have been successfully used in concrete structural members [2-4].

The bonding of thin FRP laminates exhibits an effective strengthening in tension in the critical tensile zone of concrete structures. The advantage of this system is much more easiness of application in service than the bonding of steel plates. Widespread use of carbon fiber sheets has already been observed in Japan with hundreds of field applications that include repairs of bridge beams, retaining walls, utility poles, slabs, chimneys, tunnels and other structures requiring strengthening, stabilization or seismic upgrade. Several reinforcing systems with carbon fibers have already been developed and evaluated by the research association of "CCA (Carbonfiber for Civil Application)", "CF Renaissance" and "CRS" (Carbonfiber Retrofitting System) in

Japan. In the present paper, the focus is on the experimental characterization of reinforcing effects of FRP sheets externally bonded to the bottom tensile zone of mortar and concrete specimens in terms of failure process and increased fracture toughness.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Large Concrete Specimen

The reinforcing material "FORCA Tow sheet" as shown in Fig. 1 was utilized and the bonding of glass-fiber or carbon-fiber Tow sheets to the concrete was similar to the actual spot process [6] as described in Fig. 2, where epoxy resin is used as primer for excellent bonding characteristics. Two kinds of specimens of concrete with and without center notch were prepared for the experiment. The size of the specimen was 18kg in weight, 710mm in length, 150mm in height and 75 mm in width as shown in Fig. 3, which was based on the test method of RILEM [5]. Figure 4 shows the experimental set up for three-point-flexure with a specimen and six acoustic emission (AE) transducers for moment tensor analysis [7] and two for conventional AE measurement. AE measurement was detected by 150kHz resonant-type piezo-electric transducers (PAC, R-15), stuck at suitable locations of the specimen. MISTRAS 2001 system of Physical Acoustic Corporation was utilized as AE measurement.

Fig. 1: Cross-section of "FORCA Tow sheet".

Fig. 2 : Process work of bonding of fiber- sheets on the concrete.

Fig. 3 : Details of large concrete specimen with center notch.

Fig. 4 : Experimental setup of three-point-flexure test and AE transducers for large concrete specimen.

Small Mortar Specimen

Figure 5 shows the size of the small specimen of mortar, which was based on the test method of JSME S 001 for fracture toughness; the specimen weighted 450 grams and included sand of maximum diameter 2.5mm. These small specimens were used for examining the effect of delamination between FRP layer and mortar by means of AE source location. Figure 6 shows experimental set up of three-point-flexure test of the small specimen. Conventional vinyl-ester resin was used for bonding fiber sheets without using primer resin and a 80 mm length plastic film was inserted between mortar and GFRP layer as pre-delamination.

Fig. 5 : Details of small mortar specimen with center notch.

Fig. 6 : Experimental setup of three-point-flexure test and AE transducers for small mortar specimen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Large Concrete Specimen without a Center Notch

Figure 7 shows the relation between load versus deflection curves of concrete specimen without center notch. There was no appreciable difference in the initial stiffness, which means the slope does not depend on the type of reinforcement up to 0.5 mm deflection. The experimental result, however, indicated that the theory of composite beam can be applied. There was no appreciable difference also at the initiation of non-linearity and the initiation point did not depend on the

Fig. 7 : Relation between load vs. deflection curves of concrete specimen without center notch.

type of the reinforcement. The non-linear point, naturally, was higher than for the non-reinforced specimen and was defined as the initial failure point. The initial failure point can be estimated by applying the theory of composite beam expressed by Eqn. 1, using 4.6MPa as the flexural strength of concrete without reinforcement.

$$P_{init.} = \frac{4\sigma_c \sum (E_i I_i)}{\ell E_c I_c} \quad (1)$$

After the initial failure point, the difference in the load-deflection behavior evidently shows the dependence on the reinforcement. At the final failure, the reinforcement FRP layer did not show any sign of damage, and shear failure occurred in the concrete close to the reinforcement layer as shown in Fig. 8 . By assuming that the tensile failure of the FRP layer and compressive failure of the concrete occur at the same time, the final failure load can be calculated. Figure 9

Fig 8: Typical failure mode including interfacial delamination of concrete specimen without center notch reinforced with carbonfiber sheet of two plies.

Fig 9 : Comparison of experimental and calculated final failure load for concrete specimen without center notch.

shows the comparison between experimental and calculated data. The result shows that experimental failure strength does not increase appreciably. This is because of the difference in the failure mode at final failure.

Large Concrete Specimen with a Center Notch

Figure 10 shows the typical failure mode of a reinforced specimen. Crack ① initiates and propagates vertically from the tip of the notch at first. Next, 45-degree cracks ② occur from the bottom to the center of the specimen. Finally, crack ③ at the bottom of the specimen extend from initiation point of the 45-degree crack to the direction of support of the flexural jig. The interface of the bottom crack was in the concrete and not between concrete and reinforcement

Fig. 10: Typical failure mode including notch extension, 45-degree crack and interfacial delamination of center notched concrete specimen reinforced with carbonfiber sheet of two plies.

layer, which verified the excellent bonding. Figure 11 shows the relation between load and crack opening displacement (COD). After 45-degree cracks are formed, measurement of COD became irrelevant, therefore only initial stage of the curves is displayed. To evaluate the critical load, the 5% offset procedure by the RELEM test method and the method for metallic material were used. However, stable values could not be obtained, therefore the AE technique was applied. When acoustic emissions initiated, the corresponding load was defined as " P_{AE} " as shown in Fig. 12. By using finite element analysis based on the condition of two dimensional plane strain and assuming perfect bonding of the interface between concrete and reinforcement layer, the stress intensity factor "K-value" of the notch tip was calculated based on the crack extension method by using P_{AE} as shown in Table 1. The mesh division of the FEM analysis is shown in Fig. 13. Most of the K_{IC} values were about $0.5 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$, and the difference in value was small compared to the non-reinforced specimen. Therefore the results showed that crack initiation does not depend on the reinforcement. That is to say, the crack initiation depends on the fracture toughness of concrete itself. Thus it was verified that the AE technique detects crack initiation effectively.

In the case of reinforced specimen without center notch, the FRP layer is expected to have reinforcing action. On the other hand, for specimens with center notch the FRP layer is expected to have a repair action. Figure 14 shows relation of maximum failure load for specimens without center notch and specimens with a center notch. The result indicated that is good corre-

Fig. 11 : Relation between load vs. COD curves of reinforced concrete specimen with center notch.

Fig. 12 : Typical diagram of load , AE hits activity vs. time of concrete specimen with center notch.

Table 1 : Comparison of experimental P_{AE} and stress intensity factor K_{IC} calculated by FEM.

	GF: 1ply	GF: 2plies	CF: 1ply	CF: 2plies	Concrete
P_{AE} (N)	3860	6260	6220	8090	2350
K_{IC} (MPa $m^{1/2}$)	0.424	0.561	0.499	0.518	0.595

Fig. 13 : Mesh division of the FEM analysis for the specimen.

lation between the reinforcing effect and the repairing effect.

For specimens with a center notch reinforced by FRP layer, K_{IC} is defined as inherent fracture toughness of concrete alone, K_{IM} is defined as the apparent fracture toughness of the reinforced specimen, and K_{IP} is the apparently increases in fracture toughness induced by the reinforcement. So the relation between K_{IC} , K_{IM} and K_{IP} can be expressed as Eqn.2. The effect of reinforcing " K_{IP}/K_{IC} " was calculated as shown in Table 2. The results indicate that the effect of reinforcement improves according to the increase in stiffness of the reinforcement.

$$K_{IC} = K_{IM} - K_{IP} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 14 : Relation of maximum failure load between specimen without center notch versus specimen with a center notch.

Table 2 : Reinforcing effect " K_{IP}/K_{IC} ".

	GF: 1ply	GF: 2plies	CF: 1ply	CF: 2plies
K_{IP}/K_{IC}	1.30	1.82	2.15	2.95

To classify crack type and to determine crack orientation in the concrete specimen, the moment tensor analysis is an effective method [7], which is a quantitative AE waveform analysis based on the moment tensor modeling of cracks. This analysis was applied here. Computer programs called MI-TRA and SIGMA were used to analyze the sets of AE waveforms recorded during the test. The results are plotted in Fig. 15 a,b. Orientations of tensile crack are shown by arrows, and shear cracks are given by crosses. One of the two orientations of the crosses corresponds to the direction of shear crack motion. Although composition of the concrete is non-homogeneous as shown in Fig. 16, the result of the analysis are apparently in good accordance with the failure mode. The arrows (tensile) mainly exist near the tip of the center notch, and the crosses (shear) exist in the lower part of the specimen.

Fig. 15a : Crack type and orientation in the glassfiber 1-ply reinforced concrete specimen analyzed by the moment tensor method (left) and the failed specimen (right).

Fig. 15b Crack type and orientation in the carbonfiber 1-ply reinforced concrete specimen analyzed by the moment tensor method (left) and the failed specimen (right).

Small Mortar Specimen with a Center Notch

The small specimen of mortar was used to characterize a delamination failure process using the Acoustic Emission technique. Since primer resin was not used for bonding of FRP layer, the interfacial strength was lower compared to that of the large concrete specimen. Therefore delamination at the interface occurred easily. Figure 17(a)(b) shows the time history of AE hits and applied flexural load. The first AE peak “regions ① to ②” corresponds to extension of the center notch. The second AE peak “regions ③ to ④” corresponds to extension of interfacial delamination between the two supports of the flexural jig. After the second peak of AE activity, the activity decreased, which means that the interface between the sup-

Fig. 16 Non-homogeneous cross section of a concrete specimen.

Fig. 17 Diagram of load (a), AE activity (b) vs. time for center-notched reinforced mortar specimen.

Fig. 18 : Change of AE source location by one-dimensional, two-sensor measuring method for center-notched reinforced mortar specimen.

ports had delaminated completely. The final AE peak "region ●" corresponds to extension of delamination at the interface of the overhang of the specimen. Figure 18 (a) (b)(c)(d)(e) indicates the AE source location on the specimen. By extracting the events and analyzing them at the AE source locations for specific period, the crack extension at the center notch and even the extension of interfacial delamination could be detected effectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The failure process and reinforcing effects of concrete and mortar specimens strengthened externally by bonding FRP sheets to the bottom tensile zone were characterized experimentally. The experimental results indicated that the reinforcing effects by FRP sheets improved with the increase in stiffness of the reinforcement. It was verified that AE technique detects crack initiation, source location and can be used to classify crack type and orientation effectively.

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